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FACTORS AFFECTING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the internal and external factors affecting the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises. It highlights the importance of investment, innovation, labor productivity, and efficient use of resources in improving economic efficiency. In addition, the impact of digitalization processes and management efficiency on enterprise performance is assessed.

Keywords: Industrial enterprise, economic efficiency, investment, innovation, labor productivity, competitiveness, resource utilization, digitalization, management efficiency, production costs, modernization, economic growth.

Industrial production is considered a leading sector of the national economy, and ensuring economic development through improving the economic efficiency of enterprises is a key issue. The increasing global competition, resource scarcity, and deepening market relations require new approaches to improving the results of industrial enterprises' economic activity. In particular, reducing production costs, increasing labor productivity, introducing innovative technologies, and strengthening investment activity are becoming urgent tasks for enhancing the competitiveness of enterprises. In Uzbekistan, ongoing reforms aimed at modernizing industrial sectors, developing the digital economy, and expanding export potential make it necessary to conduct in-depth research on the factors affecting the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises.

Issues of improving the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises occupy an important place in economic research. In this field, extensive studies have been conducted by foreign and local scholars on the essence of efficiency, its evaluation indicators, and the factors influencing it.

In the research of George Stigler, determining the optimal level of production output and its impact on market relations is analyzed as an important factor of economic efficiency. In his study, minimizing average costs and maximizing profit are considered the main principles in organizing production output, D. A. Fedin studied the issues of strengthening market relations through the formation of an optimal production volume in industrial enterprises. According to their scientific views, the full and efficient utilization of an enterprise's production capacity reduces production costs, increases competitiveness, and ensures stable economic relations in both domestic and foreign markets. Therefore, the performance results of industrial

enterprises depend not only on the efficient organization of production but also on the quantitative and qualitative alignment of output with market demand. In this regard, sales processes and delivery conditions also have a direct impact.

Rui Xie, Xiaojuun Deng, Yuanxing Yin, Dilafruz Fayzieva, Elchin Eyvazov, and Fu Liu studied the factors affecting the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises by analyzing the impact of production cycle regulation on financial results. In their research, they considered not only technical efficiency indicators and broad economic analyses but also a comprehensive cost–benefit approach that directly determines economic value. They proposed a strong economic model that links production performance with financial outcomes. In studying production outcomes, a robust economic model was proposed that links efficiency with financial results.

Rui Xie, Xiaojuun Deng, Yuanxing Yin, Dilafruz Fayzieva, Elchin Eyvazov, and Fu Liu investigated the factors affecting the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises by analyzing the impact of production cycle regulation on financial performance. In their study, they examined not only technical efficiency indicators and broader economic analyses but also a comprehensive cost–benefit approach that directly determines economic value and overall performance. A robust economic model linking production outcomes with financial results has been proposed in the study of production performance. Therefore, ensuring the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises requires the effective utilization of production capacities, reducing production costs, and maintaining the competitiveness of enterprises. In addition, aligning production volume with market demand contributes to profit maximization and financial stability.

In some studies, the impact of efficient production cycle management on financial results has also been analyzed. In this context, overall economic performance was evaluated not only through technical efficiency indicators but also using a comprehensive cost–benefit analysis. The studies show that efficient use of resources, optimization of production processes, and improvement of product quality are among the key conditions of economic efficiency in industrial enterprises.

E. T. Yakubova studied the key aspects of factors affecting economic efficiency based on industrial product diversification using the following methodology.

$$K_d = 1 - \left[\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{x_{ij}}{X_i} \right)^2} - \sqrt{1/n} \right] / \left[1 - \sqrt{1/n} \right] \quad (1)$$

K_d - diversification coefficient;

x_{ij} - the value of products of the j-sector (technological or product group) of the i-region;

X_i - i- the total volume of industrial production of the i-region.

In the study, the diversification coefficient was used to assess the structural variety of industrial products. A higher coefficient indicates a more diversified production structure and greater economic stability. According to scientific views, expanding product types strengthens enterprises' competitiveness, improves the efficient use of resources, and enhances financial performance.

In the development of the industrial sector, the role of different industries is highly important. To assess the condition of the textile industry, we consider the grouping coefficient based on the volume of textile industrial output per capita using the following methodology.

$$T_{hk} = \frac{T_i}{T} \quad (2)$$

Here, T_{hk} - grouping coefficient of textile industrial production per capita by regions;

T_i –per capita volume of textile products in the i-region;

T - per capita volume of textile products in the country.

On the basis of assessing the level of regional variation in per capita industrial and textile production in Andijan region, the impact of the industrial sector and textile industry enterprises can be analyzed using the above methodology (Table 1).

Table 1.

Indicators of per capita industrial production in Andijan region

№	Indicators	2015-y.	2017-y.	2021-y.	2022-y.	2023-y.	2024-y.	2025-y.
1	Andijan region per capita industrial production grouping coefficient by districts	1,31	0,97	0,87	1,09	1,24	1,13	1,19
2	Andijan region per capita textile industrial production grouping coefficient by districts	1,19	0,72	1,10	1,15	1,22	1,14	1,16
3	Izoh (solishtirma tahlil)	Total industry	Total industry	Textile industry,	Textile industry,stry, Te	Total industry	Textile industry,	Textile industry, Textile

In Andijan region, the per capita industrial production grouping coefficient was 1.31 in 2015, decreasing to 0.97 in 2017 (−0.34 or −25.9%). It further declined to 0.87 in 2021 (−10.3% compared to 2017), while in 2022 a sharp increase was observed, reaching 1.09 (+25.3%). In 2023 it continued to grow to 1.24 (+13.8%), slightly decreased to 1.13 in 2024 (−8.9%), and then rose again to 1.19 in 2025 (+5.3%).

For the textile industry, the coefficient dynamics are as follows: 1.19 in 2015, a sharp decline to 0.72 in 2017 (−39.5%), an increase to 1.10 in 2021 (+52.8%), 1.15 in

2022, 1.22 in 2023 (+6.1%), a decrease to 1.14 in 2024 (-6.6%), and a slight rise to 1.16 in 2025 (+1.8%).

Overall, the results show that per capita industrial and textile production indicators in the region are not stable across districts. The industrial sector demonstrates a fluctuating trend, with periods of decline followed by recovery, indicating cyclical development and persistent regional disparities. In the textile sector, the grouping coefficient shows relatively higher variability and concentration in certain areas, reflecting growing specialization while still indicating differences in development levels across regions.

In general, the obtained results suggest that ensuring regional balance in industrial development and stabilizing the textile sector requires focusing on the following:

1. Reducing regional disparities by diversifying industrial production across territories.
2. Increasing the share of high value-added products in the textile industry.
3. Achieving balanced development of industrial infrastructure by directing investments to less developed regions.
4. Expanding cooperation and cluster systems among enterprises and introducing digital technologies and innovations to improve production efficiency.

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